

Control of helminthosporiose of rice. Rice Research Station, Pattambi, Kerala, India.

Treatment	Dose/ha	1977-78 seasons			
		Kharif		Rabi	
		Disease index (%)	Yield (t/ha)	Disease index (%)	Yield (t/ha)
Edifenphos	0.5 liter	53	1.9	57	1.3
Zineb	2.0 kg	49	2.0	53	1.4
Mancozeb	2.0 kg	54	1.9	56	1.4
Captafol	2.0 kg	55	1.8	59	1.3
Copper oxychloride	2.0 kg	53	1.8	58	1.3
Aureofungin sol	0.05 kg	56	1.9	58	1.3
IBP	1.0 liter	50	2.0	58	1.4
Control	-	59	1.7	67	1.2
CD (0.05)		n.s.	n.s.	6.71	0.114

Plants treated with mancozeb, edifenphos, and IBP were amply protected but did not give commensurate yield increases (see table). ■

Herbicides in plant disease control

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A field experiment during punja season (Oct—Feb) in cultivators' fields in Kuttanad area, Alleppey, Kerala, under the Operational Research Project, studied the influence of herbicides on sheath blight and sheath rot control. The average disease scores of sheath blight and sheath rot are given in the table.

Average scores of sheath blight and sheath rot with different herbicides. Kerala, India.

Treatment	Sheath blight score (0-9)	Sheath rot score (0-9)
2,4-D spray at 1 kg a.i./ha	2.30	2.40
2,4-D at 1 kg mixed with 50 kg urea/ha applied to soil	3.35	3.15
Weedon (18%), 5 kg mixed with 50 kg urea/ha applied to soil	2.81	2.93
Benthiocarb (Saturn) granules at 2 kg a.i./ha applied to soil	3.15	2.75
Foliar application of benthiocarb at 2 kg a.i./ha	1.50	1.98
Hand weeding (control)	3.20	2.65

Symptoms of ufra disease of deepwater rice in Bangladesh

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Three symptom types are proposed for ufra (caused by the stem nematode *Ditylenchus angustus* Filipjev) as it occurs under Bangladesh field conditions. The

Results indicate that spraying the foliage with benthiocarb (Saturn) reduced sheath blight and sheath rot.

Weeding is a problem for rice cultivation in Kuttanad. Because of the high labor cost involved in mechanical weed control, most farmers use chemical weed control. The information obtained through the present trial indicates that benthiocarb (Saturn) has an additional advantage of controlling sheath blight and sheath rot. These diseases are severe in this locality. ■

symptoms are based on the extent of panicle emergence (see figure). In ufra 1, the panicle fails to emerge; in ufra 2 the panicle exhibits partial emergence; and in ufra 3, the panicle emerges properly, but the grain remains unfilled. The categories *thor* ufra and *pucca* ufra by Butler correspond approximately to ufra 1 and ufra 3, respectively, although ufra 1 includes all panicles that fail to emerge, whether or not they also exhibit the spiral distortion characteristic of severe attack. The newly proposed

The symptoms of ufra (left to right): ufra 1, ufra 2, and ufra 3. Bangladesh Rice Research Institute, Dacca, Bangladesh.

symptom type, ufra 2, is intermediate between ufra 1 and ufra 3, but appears to be distinct. The proportion of panicles in a defined area classified as ufra 2 has been found useful as a disease index. ■

Components of yield loss from ufra

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Ufra (caused by the stem nematode *Ditylenchus angustus* Filipjev) sometimes occurs in well-defined patches within a field in southern Bangladesh. At harvest the patches are often visible from a distance because stems bearing healthy panicles lodge whereas diseased stems, supporting empty heads, remain erect. There is a distinct gradient in disease intensity across a single field.

A field of this type, about 6.5 km west of Chandina in Comilla District, was selected in November 1978. Crop-cuts of 4 m² were made in different parts of the field: 3 where disease intensity was highest, 3 where it was moderate, and 3 where it was lowest.

Results of selective crop-cuts (4 m²) in a farmer's field near Chandina, Comilla District, Bangladesh, 29 Nov 1978.

Sample no.	Panicles (no./4 m ²)					Disease index			Yield (t/ha)
	Ufra 1	Ufra 2	Ufra 3	Whiteheads	Total	Ufra I	Ufra II	Ufra III	
1	9	45	42	10	140	6	32	30	0.15
2	13	32	58	2	147	9	22	39	0.35
3	8	40	35	5	198	4	20	18	0.51
4	7	26	78	23	220	3	12	35	0.54
5	4	19	196	6	284	1	7	69	0.85
6	7	13	77	9	236	3	6	33	0.88
7	1	2	111	7	346	0	1	32	1.42
8	0	4	69	9	305	0	1	23	1.70
9	0	0	116	20	536	0	0	22	2.92

All the panicles in each quadrat were harvested; classified as either Ufra 1, Ufra 2, ufra 3 (see preceding article), whiteheads (probably due to stem borer activity), or healthy; and counted. The disease indices ufra I, II, III were defined as the number of ufra I, ufra 2, and ufra 3, expressed as a percentage of the total number of panicles present in the specified area. Each crop was threshed to estimate yield corrected to 14% moisture content (see table).

Both Ufra I and ufra II increased more or less continuously, with yield loss up to severe levels of the disease. Ufra III first increased, then dwindled as the disease intensity (as measured by ufra I or ufra II) increased. Ufra III appears unsuitable as a disease index. Ufra II is suggested as a measure of disease level because it estimates a larger proportion of the yield loss directly at moderate disease levels, it assumes nonzero values at lower loss levels, and ufra 2 is easier to detect in the field than ufra 1. The disadvantages of using ufra II as a disease index are that, even at barely detectable levels, a substantial yield loss has already occurred (this is even more true of ufra I), and the symptom type ufra 2 resembles and may be confused with fungal sheath rot associated with *Sarocladium* spp.

But the loss of panicle density (panicles/m²) is the major component of the yield loss, about equal to the loss associated with the sum of all three symptom types. For any given disease level, half of the yield loss is represented by non-present panicles and half by panicles that produce no grain. Similar results were obtained in two other fields with distinct ufra patches at the same

site in 1977, and in three other fields at different locations in 1978 (one along the Dacca-Narsingdi Road, and two east

of Hajiganj, southern Comilla). No fields were examined in 1979 because of the difficulty of finding suitable ones. ■

Simulation of an ufra attack

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Ufra (caused by the stem nematode *Ditylenchus angustus* Filipjev) is a serious disease of deepwater rice in southern Bangladesh. To make progress in understanding the disease, it is important to be able to simulate natural infestation under controlled conditions. A special deepwater tank has been built at BRRI

for use in studying the disease. In 1979, the first year of the tank's use, an ufra patch in deepwater rice was successfully reproduced.

On 10 April 1979, the deepwater rice variety Gorcha was sown in an 8- x 8-m plot in the tank and simultaneously inoculated with 100 infested panicles kept from the previous season (1.6 panicles/m²). The plot was drenched with water from the main supply to the tank soon after sowing. The tank was flooded in early June and the water depth maintained at about 0.5 m. Every 2 weeks, a random sample of 100 stems was collected with the collector's eyes

The growth of the nematode population (percentage of infested stems) in a farmer's field at Matlab Bazar and in the deepwater tank at BRRI.